

Piling Research in Belfast's soft clay

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SYNOPSIS

The paper highlights some findings from a research programme underway at Kinnegar, which is about 10km north east of Belfast city centre. The paper describes the results from instrumented precast concrete driven piles that were subjected to (a) lateral loading, (b) combined lateral and vertical loading and (c) tension loading; the tension tests were performed on a group of five piles (with a pile cap) and on a single isolated pile. The test results are shown to reveal interesting and unexpected aspects of pile behaviour in soft clay.

1.0 Introduction

This paper highlights some findings from a research programme presently underway at a Dept. of the Environment (N. Ireland) site at Kinnegar, which is about 10km north east of Belfast city centre. This programme has evolved over the past 2 years and has made use of instrumented precast concrete piles (which were cast and driven by Lowry McKinney plc.) to achieve the following primary objectives:

(i) to derive parameters for laterally loaded driven pile design in sloop and to deduce the effect of an axial load on the lateral stiffness of a pile.

(ii) to compare the response of pile groups subjected to tension, compression and lateral loading with the response of single piles and to formulate general conclusions regarding interaction effects in pile groups driven in soft clay.

(iii) to investigate cyclic and aging effects for driven piles and pile groups in soft clay.

The Institution of Civil Engineers in London awarded the Project team an ICE 'Research & Development Enabling Grant' in January 1998; this has provided a great boost to the research participants who are Trinity College, Dublin (TCD), Lowry McKinney plc, John Barnett & Assoc., Dublin and Imperial College, London. The DoE (N.I.) and Queens University Belfast are also contributing to a separate site and soil characterisation study with TCD. Two PhD students from TCD are currently working on the project.

2.0 Outline of paper

The full programme of research, including both completed and forthcoming research, is first summarised. Some information concerning the site and stratigraphy is then provided before presenting results and some preliminary conclusions from (a) lateral load tests on single piles and (b) tension tests on a pile group and a single pile. Background information concerning parallel and inter-connected research being conducted at Imperial College, London is provided in Appendix 1 of this paper.

3.0 Research programme

The research programme is subdivided into three strands, which can be summarised as follows:

(i) Field testing of piles

- Lateral and combined lateral & axial compression load tests on two instrumented single piles are completed; re-testing of these piles is scheduled for April '99.
- Tension tests on a group (comprising 5 piles) and single pile are completed.
- Five new instrumented piles are cast and will be driven in April '99; testing in compression of this group and of another single pile will take place in June/July '99.
- Lateral testing and/or cyclic loading of pile groups is expected to be completed by early 2000.
- Re-testing of single piles & pile groups is likely in early 2001.

(ii) Site and soil characterisation

- 10 No. CPT/CPTU tests and 2 No. piston sample boreholes are completed.
- Seismic cone tests (& possibly pressuremeter tests) are planned for summer 1999.
- Classification tests & conventional strength/ compressibility tests are on-going.
- Undrained and drained triaxial stress paths tests are underway.
- Simple shear, ring shear interface & 1-D constant rate of strain tests have commenced.
- The derivation of parameters for an appropriate constitutive model for sloop will begin in early 2000 following completion of all laboratory and fieldwork.

(iii) Review / development / analysis

To date, there has been only a limited amount of research aimed at extending and generalising the findings from the field tests. Work that has started (or that will start in Summer 1999) includes:

- A review of a recently compiled International Technical Committee (ITC18) database of pile group load tests
- Assembly and study of a database of lateral pile tests.
- Numerical studies of interaction effects in pile groups and combined loading of single piles
- Development of a simplified method for the prediction of pile group axial stiffness
- Extension of Imperial College's approach for single piles to the prediction of pile group capacities.

4.0 The site and stratigraphy

The site is located at Kinnegar approximately 10km to the north-east of Belfast city centre on the southern shore of Belfast Lough. The test area, which is shown on Figure 1(a), measures $\approx 200\text{m} \times 50\text{m}$ and lies adjacent to Kinnegar Sewage Treatment Plant and to the Tillysburn Gates to Belfast Harbour Industrial Estate. Figure 1(b) shows the locations of completed pile tests in addition to the locations of boreholes and Cone Penetration Tests (CPT's) performed specifically for this research project.

CPT q_c profiles recorded along the section line shown on Figure 1(b) are plotted on Figure 2. These tests and the piston sampling conducted at the locations of Boreholes 1 & 2 (as seen on Figure 1(a)) revealed a site stratigraphy comprising $\approx 0.3\text{m}$ of fill overlying $\approx 2\text{m}$ of alluvial clayey sands and silts, which, in turn, overlies $\approx 7\text{m}$ of soft, high plasticity, sensitive clay (referred to locally as 'sleech'); this clay is underlain by a medium dense sand layer. CPT q_c values in the upper alluvium are typically $\approx 1.5\text{MPa}$ while those in the sleech are in the range 150kPa to 250kPa and representative of a very soft to soft clay. The water table is 1m below the ground surface.

Tests on 100mm diameter piston samples of the sleech indicated it to have an overconsolidation ratio of 1.4 ± 0.2 and a triaxial compression undrained strength varying from 10kPa at 2.5m to 18kPa at 6m depth. Further information on the properties of the sleech will become available as the site characterisation study

progresses and can also be found in references such as Crooks & Graham (1976).

The properties and variability of the alluvium overlying the sleech have a particular importance for the interpretation of the lateral load tests discussed in the following and are best described by their CPT resistances. The CPT profile at CPTU3 (see Figure 2) is considered most representative of the properties at the locations of the lateral pile tests.

5.0 Lateral Pile Tests

5.1 Test set-up

Two 350mm square instrumented precast concrete piles, designated *L1* and *AL1*, were installed in August 1997. The piles were driven to the sand layer at 9.5m depth and load tested two months later. The test programme involved first applying an axial load of 460kN to pile *AL1*. This load, which was equivalent to the total weight of the loading frame and kentledge employed, induced a pile head settlement of 1.8mm and was maintained while subjecting both *AL1* and *L1* to lateral loading one day after application of the vertical load; these tests are designated CLT1. The lateral load tests to failure of both *AL1* and *L1*, which took place on the day following CLT1, are designated CLT2 and were conducted about six hours after the axial load on pile *AL1* had been reduced to 235kN.

The two piles, which were installed 2m apart, were loaded laterally by jacking both apart via a strut and

collar arrangement. The soil in front of each pile was removed to a depth of 0.85m, but had not been removed on the sides of the piles. The mechanism at the head of pile *AL1*, which included rollers at the underside of the beam supporting the kentledge and a pin just above the pile collar, was intended to allow both free rotation and lateral displacement at the pile head while allowing the vertical load to be carried centrally on the pile; see Figure 3.

Both piles had centrally placed inclinometer tubes which contained a string of electro-levels for monitoring the pile displacement profiles. Approximately 20 electrical resistance strain (ERS) gauges and 4 vibrating wire (VW) strain gauges were placed strategically in the reinforcement of each pile. Four pressure cells were cast into pile *AL1* to measure the lateral soil resistance provided by the sleech.

The instrumentation was highly successful and yielded repeatable and reliable data over the course of the test programme. However, the strain gauge measurements made above ground level in pile *AL1* indicated that the loading mechanism at its head did not perform exactly as intended and that some friction had resulted in the application of a (small) moment to the pile head. Fortunately, this moment was known and could be allowed for when interpreting the test results.

5.2 Displacement characteristics

The lateral load vs. lateral displacement (F- δ) responses measured during the tests in series CLT1 & CLT2 on piles AL1 & L1 are shown on Figure 4. Corresponding displacement profiles at a number of lateral load levels are shown on Figures 5 and 6.

5.2.1 Series CLT1

It is clear that there is a dramatic difference between the F- δ characteristics, with pile AL1 moving 4mm under a lateral load of 60kN while pile L1 moves 24mm under the same lateral load. Moreover, pile L1 indicates a distinctly non-linear characteristic and, on unloading, experiences a permanent lateral displacement of 8mm. The recovery of pile AL1, when unloaded, is almost complete, verifying the more elastic response of this pile.

The displacement profiles plotted in Figure 5 highlight the markedly different responses of both piles and also indicate that the vast majority of lateral resistance is offered by the soil to a depth of only 2m (or 6 pile widths). The lateral response of the piles was therefore controlled in these tests by the properties of the clayey sand and silt overlying the sleech.

5.2.2 Series CLT2

The displacement characteristics observed during Series CLT2 also indicate the comparatively high initial stiffness of pile AL1 but show that the ultimate capacity of the ground adjacent to this pile is marginally less than that adjacent to pile L1. Moreover, pile AL1 failed abruptly (at a horizontal displacement of

$\approx 15\text{mm}$), at which point the axial pile load reduced to zero due to a large rotation of the pile head assembly.

It is worth pointing out that the measured lateral capacities of piles AL1 & L1 are considerably larger than those that would be obtained if the sleech had extended to the ground surface.

5.3 Bending moment in series CLT1

Bending moments in the piles were derived from the strain measurements and use was made of the SAFE finite element program (OASYS 1997) to predict the non-linear relationship between bending moment and strain in the pile sections. This analysis indicated that moments could be derived very simply using an uncracked EI value for both piles during series CLT1.

Bending moments inferred at lateral loads of 30kN and 60kN in series CLT1 are plotted on Figure 7. These and other bending moments have been used in conjunction with the measured displacement profiles and the pressure cell readings to deduce p - y relationships for the soil horizons at Kinnegar.

5.4 Influence of axial compression load on lateral behaviour

One of the most interesting features of the data presented on Figures 4 -8 is the significantly higher lateral stiffness of the axially loaded pile (AL1). Lehane et al. (1999) include for the effect of the restraining

moment at the head of pile AL1 (e.g. see Figure 7) and present best fit p - y curves corresponding to conditions adjacent to both piles. These indicate that the apparent lateral stiffness of the ground adjacent to pile AL1 is, to a depth of about 2m, typically three times that inferred for the soil adjacent to pile L1. Such a factor on soil stiffness cannot be explained by natural variability of conditions across the site (e.g. see range of q_c values in Figure 2) and is therefore associated with the presence of the axial load. This phenomenon is currently being investigated numerically. Additional lateral tests on the piles are also scheduled to assist interpretation.

5.5 General conclusions from lateral tests

While a more complete description and initial interpretation of these test results is provided in Lehane *et al.* (1999), the following findings have immediate implications for the design of laterally loaded piles:

- Lateral pile load tests are likely to indicate a lower lateral stiffness for the soil than would be developed under combined loading in service. However, as movements increase, the presence of a vertical load may contribute to a sudden collapse.
- The response of a pile to lateral load is critically dependent on the characteristics of the soil within the top five pile diameters below the ground surface. Improving the soil stiffness in this region could be considered as a cost-effective option at the design stage.

80% dissipation of excess
pwp over 2 months.

- The assumption of zero or infinite tensile strength for concrete when estimating the flexural rigidity of a reinforced concrete section can distort the interpretation of lateral pile load test results.

- Side friction (particularly for square precast piles) plays an important role in controlling the response of piles at conventional working displacement levels.

6.0 Pile Group Tension Test

6.1 Test set-up

Phase 1 of the pile group experimental programme at Kinnegar involved tension tests on a group of five piles and a single reference pile. All piles were 250mm square precast concrete sections and were driven to 6m depth. The group comprised four outer piles, which were at a radius of 720mm from the central pile; see inset in Figure 1(b). The central pile was driven first and was subsequently re-tapped following driving of the outer piles. Pneumatic piezometers showed that maximum excess pore pressures generated by group installation (measured at depths between 2m and 5m) varied from $1.2\sigma'_{v0}$ at 1m from the group centre to $0.4\sigma'_{v0}$ at 2.5m from the group centre (σ'_{v0} is the free field vertical effective stress). 80% of all excess pore pressures had dissipated within 2 months of group installation.

Group tension loading took place 1 year after installation using the arrangement shown on Figure 8. A load cell was fitted to each pile head and welded to the steel pile cap; this

cell also provided the anchorage point for Dywidag bars that were grouted into the piles heads. The tension load was applied by pulling two high strength bars that were bolted to plates located on the underside of the pile cap. The two jacks were seated on a deep beam and the compressive supports to the applied tension load were provided by slip-coated compression piles that were driven to the sand layer at 9.5m depth and linked with a concrete cap.

A similar set-up was used for the pull-out test on the single reference pile; see Figure 9. This pile was equipped with 12 No. vibrating wire gauges to measure the distribution of axial load (gauges were located on each of the four reinforcing bars at three separate levels along the pile length).

6.2 Group vs. single pile response in tension

The tests were load controlled, with creep rates falling to below 0.24mm/hour between load increments. The overall group response under tension loading and that of the single control pile is summarised on Figure 10. It may be seen that:

- The group stiffness (kN load per pile, per mm uplift) is lower than that of the single reference pile. The centre pile (No. 3) displayed the stiffest individual response of the five piles in the group.

- The ultimate pull-out capacity of group piles is typically $\approx 15\%$ less than that of the single reference pile. Pile 1 did, however, have an ultimate

capacity similar to the single reference pile.

Although not evident from Figure 11, the centre pile attracted 50% more load than each of the outer piles up to 75% of its ultimate capacity. At this point, the rate of load increase in the centre pile reduced significantly and, at ultimate conditions, all piles (except for pile 1) effectively carried the same load. The pile cap was deduced to have behaved in a semi-flexible manner under the applied loads.

6.3 Ultimate tension capacity of single pile

The pull-out capacity of the single pile corresponded to an average adhesion value (α) of about unity (adopting the average quick undrained triaxial compression shear strength, $c_{u0} = 15\text{kPa}$). The measured distribution of ultimate shear stresses, which is plotted on Figure 12, is however not proportional to q_c (and hence c_{u0}), suggesting much higher localised values of α near the pile tip. This effect is due to the now well established 'h/R effect' which is incorporated in the Imperial College design method for the prediction of shaft capacities of driven piles (Jardine & Chow 1996). It may also be noted from Figure 12 that the residual shear stresses (i.e. prior to testing) are very small i.e. negative skin friction is not significant.

6.4 Preliminary analysis

A prediction of the response in tension of the pile group and the single pile was made using the

PIGLET computer code (Randolph 1985). This program assumes linear elastic soil behaviour and can model either fully flexible or rigid pile caps. The analyses assumed a typical design average shear modulus to shear strength ratio for the soil (G/c_u) of 150. As seen on Figure 13, which compares PIGLET's predictions for the pile group (with a flexible cap) and the single pile with the measured field response, this (G/c_u) ratio leads to a reasonable prediction (for design purposes) of the response of the single pile at typical working load levels. However, it is evident that the same G/c_u ratio when applied to pile group prediction leads to a gross under-estimate of the stiffness of each pile in the group. Such an under-prediction arises partly because linear elastic soil models overestimate interaction effects between piles in a group.

6.5 Some conclusions from tension tests

The *tension* tests have shown that for a group comprising 5No. driven piles with a spacing to pile width ratio of three that:

- Single (i.e. isolated) piles have a stiffer response than group piles.
- The centre pile in a group has a higher initial stiffness than edge piles.
- The ultimate capacity of both centre and edge piles is $\approx 20\%$ less than isolated piles.
- $\alpha \approx 1$ for single piles.
- At working loads, adoption of $G/c_u=150$ leads to a reasonable prediction of the stiffness of an isolated pile but under-estimates group stiffness considerably.
- Current linear elastic methods for

pile groups over-predict interaction effects significantly.

7.0 Final comment

The Kinnegar programme of research has indicated interesting and unexpected aspects of pile behaviour in soft clay. Further useful results should emerge in 1999 and 2000. The research programme has involved a successful and constructive combination of research institutions and industrial partners.

8.0 Acknowledgements

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9.0 References

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Appendix 1: A description of parallel research on displacement piles at Imperial College, London

Three areas of current research interest to the Imperial team working on displacement pile behaviour are summarised in the following and the inter-connection between these areas and the Kinnegar research programme is explained.

A1.1 Pile group action in clays and sands

Interaction experiments have already been carried out with fully instrumented piles in marine sand at Dunkirk, France (Chow 1995).

The Kinnegar Research Programme tackles the same issue in clays, working from a different and more direct experimental approach.

A1.2 The effects of extended aging on pile capacity

Experiments have been carried out at the Imperial College (IC) tests

sites at Dunkirk (dense sand) and Canons Park (high OCR marine London clay). These have demonstrated very large and unexpected long term gains in shaft capacity (see for example Chow et al 1997).

In both cases the gains post-dated the full equalisation of all pore pressure changes set up by pile installation. The basic physical processes that lead to these gains are currently under investigation in further research by the IC team. A study of long-term aging effects with the Belfast piles would contribute new knowledge on the processes affecting lower OCR post-glacial clays.

A1.3 Cyclic loading

It is well known that cyclic loading can lead to very significant losses in pile capacity in clays. Figure A1 shows the interactive effects of pile average load Q_{av} and cyclic amplitude Q_{cy} during cyclic loading of the firm Norwegian Haga clay (Karlsrud and Haugen 1985). The contour lines show the numbers of cycles (N) required to cause failure: under two way loading capacity can be halved by applying a significant number of cycles. Figure A2 shows data from similar tests run at the IC test site at Dunkirk. Data from local shaft shear stress measurements are plotted in the same way as Figure A1, from a limited set of tests. Clearly load cycling can also damage the capacity of piles in sand.

An extended programme of tests on 456mm diameter, 10 to 19m long steel tubular piles is now underway

at Dunkirk that includes both aging tests and cyclic loading experiments. However, almost no data exists which show how pile groups behave under cyclic loading. Cyclic tests on the Belfast piles could provide such information and would be highly valuable, particularly if combined with cyclic control tests on single piles.

A2.0 References

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Figure 1 Site Layout Plan: Overall site (top), detailed plan (bottom).

Figure 2 CPT qc profiles at Kinnegar; see section line on Figure 1(a)

Figure 3 Load test set-up for lateral tests (above)
Rolling & sliding mechanism at head of pile AL1 (above)

Load displacement profile for pile L1

Load displacement profile for pile AL1

Figure 4 Lateral load vs. lateral displacement relationships measured in series CLT1 and CLT2

Displacement profile for pile L1 (CLT1)

Displacement profile for pile AL1 (CLT 1)

Figure 5 Displacement profiles (derived from electrolevels) in lateral tests during series CLT1

Displacement profile for pile L1 (CLT 2)

Displacement profile for pile AL1 (CLT 2)

Figure 6 Displacement profiles (derived from electrolevels) in lateral tests during series CLT2

Pile L1 (series CLT1)

Pile AL1 (series CLT1)

*Positive moment - should be zero
- axial restraint
at pin*

*Compare max
moment*

Critical depth = 2m

Figure 7 Bending moments inferred at two lateral load levels during series CLT1

6 No X beams
transverse
top & bottom

Yellow beam
transverse to
main beam.
(transfer)

Figure 8 Set-up used for tension test of group

Figure 9 Set-up used for tension test of single reference pile

Load-displacement behaviour for group piles and single pile

Figure 10 Tension load vs. pile head displacement (note pile 3 is the centre pile in the group of 5)

α value = 1 for pile

Figure 11 Shear stress distribution on reference single tension pile (+ average qc profile)

PIGLET v Measured Load-displacement behaviour

Figure 12 Measured vs. predicted response in tension tests

Figures A1 & A2

Effects of cyclic loading on shaft capacity

